

FINAL REPORT

DIGITAL STORYTELLING FOR YOUNG ENVIRONMENTAL ACTIVISTS

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PROJECT SUMMARY

In collaboration with Wild Europe e.V. from Germany, and the Mioritics Association from Romania, as well as the Centre for the Protection and Research of Birds (CZIP), Black Forest Collective GmbH organized a project titled „Digital Storytelling for Young Environmental Activists.”

Within the framework of this initiative, Black Forest Collective developed a digital video course on protecting nature through storytelling. Black Forest Collective trained teachers in Romania, Germany and Montenegro to become facilitators and work with students, using a digital course that teaches them the most effective ways to create video content on environmental issues, nature protection, wildlife, biodiversity and the impacts of climate change.

In response to the future digitalisation in schools, our project combined storytelling and nature conservation, using the power of modern technologies such as smartphones. Moreover, we used this technology to inspire young people to take steps to protect the environment by creating interesting, educational and engaging video content. Young people got to apply for a European film competition, presenting their films at the film festival in Rasnov, Romania, from the 30th August to 2nd September 2023 and competing with other creators. The best 20 films were screened at a film festival, allowing the finalists to attend a European exchange program with other young creative minds in Romania for a week full of eco-oriented activities.

THE MOVIE ABOUT THE PROJECT

OBJECTIVES OF THE PROJECT

PRIMARY PROJECT GOAL

The project aims to enhance environmental activism and develop a deeper ecological understanding using modern digital methods.

SECONDARY GOALS OF THE PROJECT

1. THE STORYTELLING COURSE

To create an innovative, engaging digital course on protecting nature through storytelling. This course is contributing to the overall European goal of digitalisation. The purpose of the video course is to encourage students to tell stories about nature as a source of inspiration and education for others, publish and present their work on social media channels and spread it in their communities. The digital course aims to introduce young people to the use of modern technologies in innovative ways.

2. EUROPEAN FILM COMPETITION

To organise a European film competition for young people from all over Europe between 15-20 years old. Young people will create short films about nature protection guided by the digital course. The best 20 films will be presented at a film festival in Rasnov, Romania, allowing the finalists to attend a European exchange program with other young creative minds in Romania for a week full of eco-oriented activities.

3. TRAINING OF FACILITATORS

To train professionals (teachers, youth workers) to become facilitators and enable them to work with young people, using the digital course that teaches them about nature protection, wilderness, biodiversity, and climate change. The facilitator will multiply the project's impact and reach even more students.

4. EMPOWERING FUTURE CHANGEMAKERS

To inspire young people to become environmental activists or volunteer for local organisations to protect nature.

5. ELEVATE THE EXPERTISE

To exchange knowledge and hands-on experience between the partner organisations and us in Romania and Montenegro.

THE DIGITAL STORYTELLING COURSE "VOICES FOR CHANGE"

Our „WHY” behind undertaking this project stems from a deep commitment to environmental advocacy through the powerful medium of storytelling. Recognizing a gap in engaging the younger generation with nature, we were inspired by the belief that everyone, regardless of experience or resources, can contribute to positive change.

Black Forest Collective - a film production company that is experienced in filming, design, photography and storytelling - created a digital video course for environmental storytelling with 43 videos at an average length of 1-3 minutes, covering a range of the following topics:

PRE-PRODUCTION

Preproduction is an essential phase of filmmaking.

During preproduction, filmmakers plan and prepare every aspect of the film, from the story to the locations to the protagonist and crew. Preproduction is critical as it helps ensure the production runs smoothly and the final film succeeds.

The production is, where the magic of filmmaking truly happens, as the story's vision comes to life in front of the camera. Successful production requires strong communication and collaboration among the entire crew, from the director to the production assistants. It's an exciting and often challenging part of filmmaking, but the result is a film that audiences will love.

CASE STUDY VIDEOS

To go beyond theory and encourage hands-on experience, we've produced two case study short films exclusively filmed with smartphones. This showcases the transformative power of storytelling, illustrating that anyone armed with the techniques learned in the course can become a filmmaker.

1. CASE-STUDY VIDEO - BIRD KINGDOM (shooting in Montenegro with CZIP)

The smartphone documentary "Bird Kingdom" for the storytelling course features the Ulcinj Salina, a wetland area home to over 250 bird species. The video showcases the unique landscape and explains its importance for biodiversity and migratory birds. The expert guide, Ksenija Medenica from CZIP, leads the viewers through the Salina and explains the significance of environmental activism, highlighting the success of the SaveSalina campaign.

2. CASE-STUDY VIDEO - BISON'S RETURN (shooting in Romania with Carpathia Foundation)

The smartphone documentary features Calin Serban, a Romanian ranger from the Foundation Conservation Carpathia. Their mission is to create a wilderness reserve in southern Carpathia, Romania. A part of the project is reintroducing European bison in Romania's Fagaras Mountains after over two centuries of extinction. It's a compelling story about the critical role of the bison in revitalising ecosystems, inspiring coexistence between humans and nature, and the vital importance of biodiversity preservation.

The videos are a testament to the power of storytelling and how it can be used to raise awareness and bring attention to critical environmental issues.

POST-PRODUCTION
& SHARING

Postproduction is the final phase of filmmaking, where the footage captured during production is edited and refined into a finished film. This phase includes a range of technical processes, such as editing, colour grading, and sound design. Overall, postproduction is an essential and rewarding part of filmmaking, where the film's vision is fully realized and brought to life.

The course is divided into - theoretical and practical (take-action) parts.

The videos are embedded in the context of active learning by using guiding questions, interactive elements, and associated homework assignments. Each video in our storytelling filmmaking course has a PDF page filled with additional information to help get the most out of the course. These PDFs include tips, tasks, and other resources that complement the video content, allowing you to dive deeper into the world of nature filmmaking. By practising and doing the tasks, students can create a short video at the end of the course.

The course instructors, Sarah Ziegler and Simon Straetker bring a wealth of expertise as distinguished directors and filmmakers. Their commitment to nurturing the storytelling abilities of emerging talents makes them the perfect guides for this format.

The course and its content are accessible on a mobile-ready website (www.voicesforchange.eu), featuring videos in English. While currently without subtitles in other European languages due to time and budget constraints, we have plans to incorporate multilingual subtitles in the future.

Participants have two options on how to create a film. They can either complete the storytelling course independently and work individually or complete it with the help of the facilitators.

TRAINING OF FACILITATORS

GERMANY

The Black Forest Collective team trained partner organisations and their selected facilitators to use the digital video course. Black Forest Collective has partnered up with Nachhaltige Bildung e.V., because they work closely with schools, implementing mainly digital and sustainable projects. This partnership enabled us to work with school teachers directly. The main training of facilitators took place in Kirchzarten on the 19th of October, 2022. Some of the participated schools attended an online training of facilitators, since they were unable to attend the workshop in person.

ROMANIA

The Mioritics Association, which is experienced in school collaborations, selected partner schools in Romania for the project. Facilitator training occurred at the Schubz Center in Rasnov on January 28, 2023, with teachers attending nationwide. An online workshop via Zoom accommodated two facilitators who were unable to attend. The Mioritics Association brings a wealth of experience and passion for environmental projects to the partnership.

MONTENEGRO

CZIP, with a dedicated advocacy, education, and communication program, hosted facilitator training on February 2, 2023. Their experience in projects with schools and young people aligns seamlessly with our goals. Two enthusiastic elementary school biology teachers were selected to work with 14-year-olds.

FACILITATORS' ROLE AND IMPACT

Facilitators helped students accomplish the digital storytelling course's shared learning, training, and development objectives. Their guidance, engagement, and expertise helped them finish the film on time and achieve its intended outcomes. Facilitators have good communication skills and enjoy leading others to work together.

The facilitators have:

- Set the goal for the learning process;
- Initiated and led the conversation during the teaching;
- Encouraged student engagement, support and guided discussions and dialogues;
- Evaluated and gave constructive feedback on what has been learned;
- Helped students apply their newly acquired knowledge and skills in practical and enhanced ways.

TRAINING DETAILS AND OUTCOME

The intense 8-hour facilitator training involved workshop sessions led by the creators of the digital video course from Black Forest Collective. After the facilitator's training, five Digital Storytelling Clubs were initiated in Romania, involving high school pupils from different regions - Timișoara, Brasov (2 clubs), Craiova and Brad. The online course and the film competition were presented to 360 high school pupils. Of those, 55 actively participated by taking the course, attending club meetings, and engaging in film screenings. These students played a hands-on role in discussing environmental topics specific to their areas and crafting impactful film productions.

The clubs also hosted online and physical meetings with the project team and with Dan Dinu from PhotoLife, a Romanian filmmaker who shared his experience about developing productions about natural values and challenges in Romania and abroad. Facilitators also had regular online meetings with the project team to share their experience leading the clubs, ideas about approaching various subjects, and challenges in leading the teams to finish the productions on time. Notably, 16 short film productions resulted from the 5 months of activities, covering diverse subjects from natural values in the area of the clubs to human threats to protected areas and noise pollution.

SUSTAINABILITY BEYOND THE PROJECT TIMELINE

After the project timeline, facilitators are empowered to train other educators or youth workers in their respective countries, extending the impact of the digital package in schools and with students.

FILM COMPETITION

Since the high quality of the storytelling course was our priority, it took longer than planned to edit the 43 videos from the course. Consequently, the date of the official launch of the campaign for the nature film competition was postponed, which did not negatively impact the project's final result, the total of films submitted, and the young people's engagement.

The film competition officially launched at the beginning of March and ended on the 31st of June, 2023. The German team created a promotional video for the contest's promotion and social media posts. The project was promoted among young people from around Europe for the project target group 14-20 and also for 20 - 25.

With the promotion, we could reach more than 20,000 young individuals, generating an engagement of more than 70,000 clicks and impressions on social media posts. The goal was to extend the project's reach to a broader audience, allowing additional young people to take the opportunity to learn filmmaking and tell stories about critical environmental issues.

During this period, facilitators guided young people through creating a short video from the initial idea to the finished film.

From a global pool of around 900 submissions, we have chosen a selection of 20 films for the main project category (14-19 years) and another 20 films for the extra category (20-25 years) in our film festival. The films covered subjects from natural values in the area of the clubs to human threats to protected areas and noise pollution.

WATCH FILMS FROM PROJECT PARTICIPANTS:

<https://voicesforchange.eu/nature-stories-festival-films>

Duration of the project:
19 MONTHS

Target group:
14 – 20 YEARS

more than
20.000 YOUNG INDIVIDUALS & 70.000 CLICKS & IMPRESSIONS
reached with promotional videos and posts

global pool of
900 SUBMISSIONS

40 FILMS selected

43 VIDEO-CLASSES created for the course

NATURE STORIES FESTIVAL

30th of August –
2nd of September
Rasnov, Romania

FILM FESTIVAL

The “Nature stories Festival” took place from the 30th of August till the 2nd of September in Rasnov, Romania. The Mioritics Association from Romania took the lead as the festival’s primary organizer. They have a lot of experience with organising festivals and international exchanges.

The festival had two main objectives. One was to promote and encourage filmmaking about nature among young people in Europe and beyond. The second one was to add to the project’s environmental education and activism component by offering the teenagers an integrated experience of discovering, reflecting on, and debating about nature.

Therefore, the festival involved screenings of pre-selected films made by young people from Europe each day. We selected creators of the best movies to join the film festival in Rasnov, Romania. On the last day of the film festival, the jury announced the festival winners, and we screened the winning film of the competition. The winning film of the category 14-19 years old, “Taking you to a hidden place” was made by Iva Otaševic and Andrej Brnovic from the primary school Radojica Perovic, Podgorica from Montenegro.

We had two juries at the festival: The Professional Jury consisted of Dan Dinu, Johanna Jaurich, Jutta Gruber-Mannigel, Simon Straetker and Nevena Petkovic. The Young jury consisted of Alexandra Ulianu, Mara Popa and Daria Cojanu, teenagers of the Rasnov Europe Direct Volunteer Club, facilitated by the Mioritics Association. Hereby, we also allowed young people to have a critical opinion and view of the films enlisted in the competition. Furthermore, the audience members present at the film screenings could cast an anonymous audience vote, which was announced on the festival’s last day. This way, the teenagers participating in the festival could see the differences in criteria and value appreciation between the different juries and see how all opinions can be given room for exposure. Here is the list of all winners from the film festival: <https://www.naturestoriesfestival.com/winners>.

Apart from the films created by young people, we presented documentaries produced by professionals. There were six short films from Wild Europe, e.V., of 30 minutes. Black Forest Collective and local film experts offered photo and video workshops answering the needs of the students. They also showed behind the scenes of creating the storytelling course and screened the two case study short films. We showed films made by Dan Dinu about Romania’s nature and wildlife. He also had a workshop session about different camera traps and filming wildlife in nature.

The screening of films per day was around 90 - 120 minutes long. We set up the dialogue between generations by bringing together young people and professionals from different fields. Subsequent discussions with the directors of the movies accompanied the film festival. It raised awareness and sensitisation about environmental protection topics among the general film festival attendees.

In parallel to the technical workshops, we organised nature-experiencing activities in the forests and hills surrounding Râșnov town and an indoor session focused on the environmental values and problems from each of the three countries, Germany, Montenegro and Romania. All teenagers and facilitators participated in this learning experience which offered insight into the challenges nature and people face in Western and Eastern European countries.

Partner organisation CZIP from Montenegro presented the richness of biodiversity in the central region of Montenegro by screening the three BioVal movies that CZIP made. Also, the potential of tourism based on nature was presented, focusing on the northern part of Montenegro with its beautiful mountains, pastures, forests and wildlife.

MONTENEGRO

From Montenegro, 11 youngsters, two teachers and Nevena Petkovic from CZIP joined the film festival. For some participants, it was the first travel abroad in their lives.

GERMANY

Regrettably, young people from Germany couldn’t attend the film festival due to various constraints. Factors such as ongoing academic commitments and school policies prevented their physical presence. Despite this, we ensured their engagement by informing them about the festival proceedings and providing feedback on their films. A link to view all films was shared, and a selected screening took place in their classroom.

ROMANIA

Fifteen teenagers from the 5 Digital Storytelling clubs from Romania and three facilitators participated in the film festival. They were happy to assist in the screenings of 5 out of the 16 club movies selected, which made it into the final selection of the 14-19-year-old section of the competition.

FESTIVAL PROGRAM

29.08.2023, TUESDAY | ARRIVAL DAY

Participants traveled to Rasnov using sustainable means of transport, either by train, or bus.

30.08.2023, WEDNESDAY | FIRST DAY OF ACTIVITIES

- 10:00 – 13:00 Amza Pellea Cinema, Welcome words and sustainability workshop
- 13:00 - 14:00 Lunch break
- 14:30 – 16:30 Amza Pellea Cinema, workshop Film Club's experience (presentations of the club's productions and of the experience of being part of the project, using the storytelling course and creating their film)
- 16:30
- 17:00 – 19:30 Amza Pellea Cinema, workshop How to use camera traps for making films about nature run by Dan Dinu (Romania)
- 20:30 Amza Pellea Cinema, film screening Wild Romania, Romania 2022, 123 min.

31.08.2023, THURSDAY

- 10:00 – 13:00 Schubz Garden, workshop Creating a Short Film with Your Smartphone run by Sarah Ziegler and Simon Straetker (Germany)
- 11:00 – 13:00 Schubz Garden, workshop Sharing Nature activities run by Luminita Tanasie and Florentina Florescu (Romania)
- 14:30 Amza Pellea Cinema, Wildlife and eco-tourism in Montenegro (screenings and discussions)
- 15:30 Amza Pellea Cinema, Wanderer Sheep 2.0 project presentation and exhibition
- 16:30 Amza Pellea Cinema, screenings of the short films competition (category 14 – 19 years)
- 19:00 - 20:00 Dinner, traditional food from the region. During this time jury discussed the winner for category 14-19 years old).
- 21:00 Schubz Garden, special event Correspondence - a musical journey around the world

1.09.2023, FRIDAY

- 10:00 – 13:00 Schubz Garden, workshop Creating a Short Film with Your Smartphone run by Sarah Ziegler and Simon Straetker (Germany)
- 11:00 – 13:00 Schubz Garden, workshop Sharing Nature activities run by Luminita Tanasie and Florentina Florescu (Romania)
- 14:30 Amza Pellea Cinema, behind the scenes of creating the storytelling course and screening the two smartphone documentaries. Film screening Wild Europe series, presented by directors Sarah Ziegler and Simon Straetker, 2019 - 2023, 60 min.
- 15:30 Amza Pellea Cinema Special screening Between coal and climate, director Johanna Jaurich, 2019, 30 min. Q&A with Johanna Jaurich
- 16:00 Amza Pellea Cinema, screening of the short films competition (category 20 – 25 years)
- 18:00 Dinner, During this time jury discussed the winner for category 20 - 25.
- 20:00 Schubz Garden, Award ceremony

2.09.2023, SATURDAY

- 18:00 Amza Pellea Cinema, film screening Into the wild, director Sean Penn, USA 2007, 148 min.

TESTIMONIALS ABOUT THE PROJECT FROM STUDENTS

„The whole project was a completely new experience for me; I've learned a lot about the ins and outs of filmmaking and everything that goes along with it, whilst making friends with a lot of awesome people in the process. If I could, I'd do it all over again!”

DARIUS CHIFOR | Brad Highschool, Romania

The course definitely answered a lot of questions I had regarding filmmaking and made me learn how to enjoy each and every step of creating a movie.

ȘTEFANIA DRĂGANCEA | Craiova Highschool

As a person who is a little bit afraid to experience challenging things, I have to admit the project had a significant impact on me! It encouraged me to dream big and have more confidence in my powers!

ANDRA DAN | Craiova Highschool

This project made me understand Nature better and make all the necessary connections to truly appreciate its importance in our lives. We often forget that we cannot exist without nature and that we are part of it. It does not belong to us; we belong to IT. Our arrogance has taken us to invent absolute comfort. But it also made us forget that we breathe nature, eat nature and ARE nature!

LIVIA POPESCU | Facilitator

The whole festival was just amazing. Everyone was wonderful, I got the chance to make great friends and memories I'll cherish for life. This being the first time I came in contact with the professional filmmaking field, it gave me a great insight into the filmmaking experience!

ANDRA DRAICA | Timișoara Highschool

The course was a great opportunity to learn valuable documentary-making and storytelling skills. Throughout the course, we were able to learn all the important things from the professionals. It was interesting and easy to understand.

NIKOLINA RONČEVIĆ | Montenegro

I liked the lecture, I especially liked that it was in a foreign language. Filming short films, and creating slogans are only a small part of everything we experienced; the people who taught us were calm and ready to answer our questions. I would like to go again and have it be the same.

MIA POTPARA | Montenegro

A filmmaking course is an inspiring experience where we learn to create compelling loglines and develop hands-on filmmaking skills, connecting with industry experts and peers to pursue our cinematic dreams.

TAMARA RAJKOVIĆ | Montenegro

It was great, I learned how to make a short film and photography, and the most interesting thing for me was slow-motion recording. Sarah, Simon and Domča are all great presenters and I would love to experience this again.

ĐORĐIJE JOKSIMOVIĆ | Montenegro

The workshops we attended during our stay in Rasnov were very interesting and instructive. We exchanged a lot of information with teachers and friends from other countries. Apart from that, socializing was very interesting and fun. A nice experience that I will remember for the rest of my life.

NIKOLINA JANJUŠEVIĆ | Montenegro

DISSEMINATION PHASE

The dissemination phase played a crucial role in extending the project's reach and impact. Leveraging online channels, social media, and strategic partnerships, we effectively communicated the project's results and engaged a broad audience.

GERMANY

The project maintained an active online presence through its dedicated website (www.voicesforchange.eu), regularly updated with project developments, participant stories, and educational resources.

- Video about the whole project <https://vimeo.com/blackforestcollective/dbu>
- Social media campaign for the course (www.instagram.com/voicesforchange.eu)
- <https://www.youtube.com/@voicesforchange-eu>
- https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZKVaSr3ppGs&list=PLktcLqzM8aUMc84N7Qlh2zXVWuuzcD-9F&ab_channel=Voicesforchange
- https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ahLD4Pn29cQ&list=PLktcLqzM8aUMftxDb23QfYdure6QmV-wn&ab_channel=Voicesforchange
- https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=r6LsUWjMEg&list=PLktcLqzM8aUNYUoWA2ipkGTjB1zVn6aiP&ab_channel=Voicesforchange
- <https://fb.watch/qm9LB0MXNh/>
- <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7066747560991846400/>

ROMANIA

Media coverage of the Nature Stories Festival:

- <https://www.radiovacanta.ro/evenimente/prima-editie-nature-stories-festival-a-inceput-astazi-la-rasnov-15294.html>
- <https://transilvania365.ro/nature-stories-festival-un-eveniment-dedicat-naturii-si-iubitorilor-de-natura/>
- <https://stiriletransilvaniei.ro/2023/08/30/la-rasnov-incepe-prima-editie-a-nature-stories-festival-un-eveniment-dedicat-naturii-si-oamenilor-care-iubesc-natura/>
- <https://newsbv.ro/nature-stories-festival-prima-editie-la-rasnov-filme-despre-natura-la-cinema-amza-pellea-si-in-gradina-schubz/>
- <https://www.agerpres.ro/cultura/2023/08/30/brasov-filme-despre-natura-in-prima-editie-a-nature-stories-festival-la-rasnov--1161676>
- <https://bzb.ro/stire/un-festival-dedicat-naturii-si-oamenilor-care-iubesc-natura-a189769>
- <https://www.ziareonline24.ro/nature-stories-festival-la-rasnov-590749/>
- <https://www.ziarelive.ro/stiri/nature-stories-festival-prima-editie-la-rasnov-filme-despre-natura-la-cinema-amza-pellea-si-in-gradina-schubz.html>
- <https://www.monitorulexpres.ro/2023/08/31/nature-stories-festival-la-rasnov/>
- <https://www.moviebloc.com/news/64f02a233f80b15abca87825/ro>

- <https://www.radioromaniacultural.ro/emisiuni/cu-minte-de-weekend/cu-minte-de-weekend-povesti-si-experien-te-pentru-suflet-id38424.html>
- Festival Facebook Page - total reach 3651
- <https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100092603446541>

MONTENEGRO

- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jQ7T9pzEWWU>
- https://www.facebook.com/watch/?extid=CL-UNK-UNK-UNK-IO5_GK0T-GK1C&mibex-tid=MnnKW6&v=1032553607873323 (From 1:24)
- https://youtu.be/SrSdkKoh8SI?si=f3FGVT2NcFP_MxHb (From 1:23)
- Short films from participants from Montenegro: https://www.youtube.com/@czip_montenegro/videos

REPORTS

- <https://www.cdm.me/kultura/film-daka-os-radojica-perovic-o-gorici-odnio-pobjedu-na-festivalu-u-rumuniji/>
- <https://rtcg.me/vijesti/drustvo/464785/nagrada-za-najbolji-kratki-film-o-prirodi-djacima-os-radojica-perovic.html>
- <https://www.portalanalitika.me/clanak/na-skriveno-te-vodim-mjesto-kratki-film-o-gorici-pobijedio-na-festivalu-u-rumuniji>
- <https://www.pcnen.com/porta/2023/09/05/film-o-gorici-odnio-pobjedu-na-festivalu-u-rumuniji/>
- <https://czip.me/film-o-gorici-odnio-pobjedu-na-festivalu-u-rumuniji/>
- <https://rtnk.me/kultura/film-djaka-os-radojica-perovic-o-gorici-odnio-pobjedu-na-festivalu-u-rumuniji/>

MOVIES PROMOTED ON CZIP FB AND INSTAGRAM PAGE

- <https://www.facebook.com/czip.cg/posts/pfbid09JesibUvtNouMc9zChYw2fftdhnHgReQpgxCz8X2FrNRvcWnGCv4fcvncLHC9q5Hlpfbid09JesibUvtNouMc9zChYw2fftdhnHgReQpgxCz8X2FrNRvcWnGCv4fcvncLHC9q5Hl>
- https://www.instagram.com/p/CyNzVEultUn/?fbclid=IwAR1ZOKzPbMWCUGYgIbtNa2zv-B7uJQpzN-pYfdkp4R9JzEdklv_ewRh-2YqM
- <https://www.facebook.com/czip.cg/posts/pfbid0Jn69AyuygAbxtgVgXgYe43Lfx3nlpLjXp4dZpxvhnayFo-riNsTdRFs5jJ95Ycral>
- https://www.instagram.com/p/Cxko_ZglJ_9/?fbclid=IwAR12qXUcYlt9oOR7ksV0GXyIDZ7DgQY2Nwhkd4j2V-BqL5YzmlOpleTi5pU
- <https://www.facebook.com/czip.cg/posts/pfbid02b5XA5VPryYs92UuWRVWZeH3SaPsyY1io1nYBn51mDBNjak-VFi2BnW4ghDe4CFwidl>
- https://www.instagram.com/p/Cw3JC6lrc2S/?fbclid=IwAR1aP_s2FmbCTi0sf3uepJ7022XGrnCSMkr-b7EFF9GHy-ltZb_WO4hlpWnw
- <https://www.facebook.com/czip.cg/posts/pfbid0319mjEbgUBU8nePPB1KB2keDnEaSyjasKqsYk1wkJMxs9Noa-GiS6WxBPsySd7x1l>
- <https://www.instagram.com/p/CwxUY3RloxC/?fbclid=IwAR0ODXtzM0cfNSD6Rvxy6KT3R4zjnCfhEn-kegDMwcm3Ml9sc08g1HP9kAY%20https://www.facebook.com/OS.Dr.Dragisa.Ivanovic/posts/pfbid0cAsDcuX1jss-jRj7KJH226w3mtEWhviMDtzZ3MBTBpPwAXTStzLvVBhsvA4jz3PKl>
- <https://www.facebook.com/osradojica.perovic/posts/pfbid0xLj3f7svGw412tn39hKAaqMt3S8svdnhExuPvty7fbQw-cCP2v8Ji2xnATcMW3CVI>

FILM SCREENING ON THE DZADA FILM FEST IN THE CAPITAL OF PODGORICA

- <https://www.facebook.com/100066404594361/posts/pfbid02qa5S9r4DK2P5qYbAYA2a2EjvJ1WE9vdeCwooaBhbyx-vPaSoaQxvUjvBokZTkjmJkl/?mibextid=cr9u03>

The facilitators organized a film screening in their school:

- <https://www.roditeљи.me/blog/2023/09/18/eko-filmski-dan-u-dvoristu-os-radojica-perovic/>
- <https://www.facebook.com/osradojica.perovic/posts/pfbid0fayFyu8Uvfrb9vqkxXkrPjjAWJZ8QEz37eMKXuoAYLax-8Hqu8CidhPYgyYtP8m9l>
- <https://www.facebook.com/OS.Dr.Dragisa.Ivanovic/posts/pfbid02ShktquT8JmXgN299fWoxYpmdtrXG2Uyh-HJEdQb1Xx3m4WrbMCZ21JLhaGvf58edYl>

RESULTS

ONLINE STORY-TELLING COURSE: A CORNERSTONE OF SUCCESS

The outcomes of the project were comprehensive and impactful. Creating an independent online storytelling course for young environmental activists became a cornerstone of the project's success. The storytelling course is in English and therefore available to use by any school in Europe and internationally.

FACILITATOR TRAINING: MULTIPLYING IMPACT

The training of facilitators ensured the course's effective multiplication in schools across participating countries. 15 facilitators from Germany, Montenegro, and Romania were trained. We have established long-lasting partnerships with various schools.

FILM FESTIVAL SHOWCASING YOUTH CREATIONS

Short films submitted by young participants (14-19 years old) were showcased at the film festival and made accessible on the "Voices for change" website for broader viewing. Facilitators and the participating students organized film screenings at their schools to screen the films created by all young people.

The project significantly contributed to increasing awareness among young people about the importance of biodiversity and wilderness, achieved through the innovative use of technology and storytelling.

Creation of a project website, www.voicesforchange.eu.
Social media campaign for the course (www.instagram.com/voicesforchange.eu).

INCREASED ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS

Raising awareness and sensitization about environmental protection topics among the general film festival attendees.

COOPERATION PARTNERS

In Montenegro - National Parks of Montenegro and NGO Gorica Association
In Romania - Schubz Center and Photo Life (Dan Dinu)
In Germany - Wild Europe e.V. and Nachhaltige Bildung e.V.

PUBLIC RELATION

We published the selected films from participants on the "voices for change" website and CZIP published films from Montenegrin participants on their YouTube channel. We promoted the project results through press releases, TV appearances, social media, and screening movies in schools.

Our future plans involve maintaining and updating the 'Voices for Change' website, as well as the social media platform. Additionally, we aim to explore partnerships with educational institutions and organizations, further training more facilitators and integrating the 'Voices for Change' storytelling course into school curriculum. By fostering continuous collaboration, expanding our network, and exploring additional avenues for dissemination, we strive to extend the project's positive influence beyond its initial timeline.

PROJECT CONTINUATION

The project will continue beyond the project period. We continue promoting the storytelling course "voices for change" among schools, young people, and on social media. The project has met with a lot of interest in incorporating it into the school curriculum, which is challenging, especially in Germany. We presented the project at a summit for high school directors in Baden Württemberg, Germany, and we received positive feedback and contacts from interested and motivated directors. We plan to continue to train facilitators who can multiply the project and support young people in creating their movies.

After the project timeline, Black Forest Collective held several workshops about filmmaking with a smartphone and telling stories about nature. CZIP prepared a design for posters and bookmarks that will be distributed to interested elementary and middle schools in Montenegro for further promotion of the storytelling course and project sustainability. Mioritics Association continues doing activities that follow the same digital storytelling objectives.

We are looking for further funding for the project to expand the idea. We will regularly update the website with the video storytelling course. The project's long-term goal is to grow the Voices for change community and dialogue with future, preferably young contributors (14 - 30 years old). We will continue building partnerships with NGOs and schools around Europe to train youth workers and teachers to become facilitators who can work with the digital course in schools or other institutions.

Participants from the film festival can persist in organizing screenings within their schools. Simultaneously, we maintain an active presence, consistently presenting the project on our social media platforms and in various press outlets.

POTENTIAL FUTURE CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS

Regarding the film festival, the subject of the film festival, stories of nature and people linked with nature, has great potential, but the format of the festival has to be improved. Young amateurs can't continue doing film festivals because it is hard to attract sponsors. We will look for a solution, such as long-term funding or to adapt the age group of the festival to attract sponsors. If we find another funding source for the film festival, we will continue organizing it because it is needed in the market in Romania.

DISCUSSION

TO WHAT EXTENT WERE THE GOALS ACHIEVED?

1. The project aimed to enhance environmental activism and develop a deeper ecological understanding using modern digital methods.

Young people from Europe have used the storytelling course to learn to tell stories about important environmental topics. Through that, the ecological understanding was strengthened and they developed digital skills.

2. We created an innovative, engaging digital course on protecting nature through storytelling. The video course encouraged students to tell stories about nature as a source of inspiration and education for others. We published their work on social media and the website to spread it in their communities and worldwide. The course introduced young people to an innovative way to use digital technologies.

3. The film festival aimed to inspire the creation of short films about nature protection. Under the guidance of our digital course, young participants, assisted by facilitators, not only completed the course but also brought their vision to life by crafting short films. The Mioritics Association has a lot of experience organizing film festivals. They have prepared a „call for films,“ document and rules for the film competition. The competition officially started on the 15th of March. It ended on the 31st of June, so the selected participants had enough time to prepare for travel to the film festival in Romania.

We created two categories to cater to a wider audience: 14 - 19 and 20 - 25. This decision aligns with CZIP's involvement with teachers with students in their classes aged 14. The upper age limit was extended beyond 20 to enhance the film festival's visibility and extend the project's reach to a more diverse audience.

4. From the Black Forest Collective, we trained professionals (teachers, youth workers, older students) to become facilitators and enable them to work with young people, using the digital course that teaches them about nature protection, wilderness, biodiversity, and climate change.

5. Young people who joined our project are more aware of the environmental problems in their countries and their communities. They are inspired to volunteer in local projects and are keen to inspire their peers from school.

6. Knowledge and practical experience were shared through collaborative interactions with partner organizations in Romania and Montenegro. This exchange enhanced the effectiveness of our joint initiatives.

COLLABORATION BETWEEN ORGANISATIONS

In May 2022, we met with the Mioritics Association, where we discussed the project, planned activities and the online schedule of meetings. Subsequently, a virtual meeting in the summer of 2022 brought together both partner organizations to fine-tune the schedule of our planned initiatives.

In September 2022, we met with CZIP in their Podgorica office to film the first case study about Ulcinj Salina (see page 9). We had regular online meetings held monthly and more frequently when necessary.

In an online meeting in November and December 2022, we mainly discussed the working methods and planned activities and divided different tasks. Black Forest Collective GmbH, a film production company, is experienced in filming, graphic design, photography and storytelling. Mioritics Association are experienced in education, non-formal education, cultural exchanges, film festivals and organizing events. They also have much experience working with schools, being Romania's only extracurricular education for sustainable development centre. Meanwhile, CZIP from Montenegro is experienced in environmental education, working with kids and nature conservation. Such a project needs to have diverse project partners. CZIP has a lot of knowledge about birds and other biodiversity members and experience in nature-related projects.

Working with diverse partner organisations is a great advantage since we are experienced in different fields, share knowledge and learn from each other. Although all partners work in diverse sectors, we work on eye-to-eye connections.

Black Forest Collective expanded its horizons as a film production company, gaining insights into working closely with schools and nature-related projects. In turn, the Mioritics Association and CZIP reaped the benefits of enhanced digital skills and knowledge through their active participation in the project.

In conclusion, our collaborative journey has been marked by shared expertise, open dialogue, and a commitment to mutual learning.

CONCLUSION

The project successfully achieved its goals by creatively combining digital storytelling, technology, and nature protection while empowering young people and fostering environmental awareness.

The cooperation with partner organisations was very enriching. In the future, we want to strengthen our collaboration with schools and educational organisations, especially in Germany.

We've established a community of passionate young advocates interested in nature conservation and storytelling. To educate more people and inspire change worldwide, the „Voices for Change“ online storytelling course is accessible to all at www.voicesforchange.eu. This platform empowers anyone to create films addressing environmental issues, providing the tools to bring their stories to life.

Reflecting on the approach, it has proven successful, although not without challenges. Time management, particularly with German schools, posed difficulties, prompting adjustments in our course timeline. We have delayed the course completion, because we decided to do more videos than intended for a better learning experience. However, there was no need for fundamental changes. It was not easy to find any available schools for cooperation in Germany eventhough we had established a partnership with NGO Nachhaltige Bildung. Mainly because of the pandemic, there are some issues with a lot of schools in Baden Württemberg. Luckily, we attended the director summit, where we met with interested teachers and directors from various high schools and got in contact with their students directly from around Germany. Although we had to make minor changes, there is no need to change the overall objectives.

In the end, the positive outcomes far outweigh the challenges, affirming the project's resilience, adaptability, and enduring impact. The community we've built and the widespread accessibility of the storytelling course on nature protection stand as testaments to the project's success in fostering environmental stewardship among the youth.

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